

Adaptability of a generic wave energy converter to different climate conditions

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This study evaluates the influence of wave climate tunability on the performance of a generic Wave Energy Converter (WEC) for different climate scenarios. The generic WEC is assumed to be composed of an array of heaving, floating cylinders. In this study, two natural periods for the cylinders of 4 s and 8 s (typical of enclosed seas and the mean Atlantic swell, respectively) and a location-tunable cylinder are considered to evaluate the influence of tuning on the power performance of the cylinder. The WEC power matrix is computed using a frequency domain model, and the performance of the WEC is evaluated along the global coasts; the met-ocean data originated from the global reanalysis database (GOW) from Reguero et al (2012). The performance of the WEC is evaluated using two parameters: the capture width ratio (CWR), which evaluates the efficiency of the converter at each location, and the kW/Ton (KWT) parameter, which evaluates the efficiency of the converter using “economic” terms. Tuning a converter for each location displayed a positive CWR; however, the KWT was low after WEC tuning because of the weight of the structures required to tune the converter that experiences high peak periods.

Keywords: adaptability; tuning; wave energy converter; resonance; capture width ratio

1. Introduction

By contrast to wind energy, an abundance of technologies exist in the wave energy sector, and a dominant technology has not emerged. Many developers are testing inventions and simultaneously optimizing the power absorption characteristics to achieve commercial prototypes. Nevertheless, uncertainty remains for this topic, and solutions could be either global or site specific.

In the optimization process, a key parameter is the wave power absorbed by the device. To maximize the Wave Energy Converter (WEC) power absorption, the local wave climate must be considered. The main assumption for the optimization scheme is that the maximum annual power absorption is obtained when the WEC natural period matches the most probable sea-state period at the point of interest.

Extensive research investigating the optimization and tuning of wave energy converters has been performed in recent years. For instance, two main methods for tuning a device were previously studied: geometry tuning (which affects the natural period of the device) and the Power Take Off (PTO) control (which has the ability to alter the absorption characteristics over time) (1). Additionally, a previous study investigated the geometry tuning procedure; that study tuned a bottom hinged flap to the prevailing wave frequency by experimenting with modifying the inertia (2). The sensitivity of the resonant frequency to slight changes in the geometry was analyzed using a new numerical model (3). Finally, a procedure for optimizing the geometries of a generic heaving wave energy converter was presented (4). These investigations demonstrated that optimizing the geometry of the tuning process is a key step in maximizing the power absorption of any WEC. In (5) an geometry optimization tool was developed in order to match the geometry of the device to the predominant wave spectrum on the area of study.

The annual power production of a WEC depends on the local wave climate and the power matrix of the WEC. As indicated above, the ideal case to maximize power production is to match the most probable sea states with higher production in the power matrix. This matching is achieved by tuning the resonant frequency of the WEC with the most probable sea state frequency.

Apart from tuning the resonant frequency of the WEC with the most probable frequency, the shape and characteristics of the power matrix also greatly influences the performance of a WEC at a given location.

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Different types of WECs were studied (6), and the displayed differences on power matrices resulting from the WEC type depended on the absorption principle and the geometry of the converter.

Therefore, in the design and optimization of a WEC, the met-ocean conditions of the potential deployment sites must be considered. To maximize the potential economic revenue, WECs should be able to be deployed in as many locations as possible. Each site has different met-ocean conditions; therefore, maximizing the number of potential deployment sites may be attained through geometrically tuning WECs.

Globally, wave climate conditions are highly variable, and wave parameters (i.e., significant wave height, H_s , and peak period, T_p) have different values depending on the location. To date, no study has investigated the best adaptability strategy of WECs to different ocean climate scenarios. Whether a unique solution for all locations or a customizable design (variable depending on the location) is appropriate has not been addressed. Currently, no analysis is available investigating which of the following methods is economically favorable: 1) developing WECs tuned for each location, 2) deploying unique broadband WEC that are valid for a high number of locations or 3) implementing site-tunable WECs.

This paper presents a study investigating the geometric adaptation of a generic WEC to different global climate scenarios. Two non-adaptive solutions and a customizable solution (variable resonant characteristics) are globally tested to analyze the improvements in power production resulting from the tuning mechanism. Performance is assessed based on two parameters: the capture width ratio (CWR) and the kW/Ton indicator. CWR represents the efficiency of the conversion in percentage with respect the incident wave resource and the Kw/Ton indicator represents the average power with respect the ballast weight of the converter.

This paper is structured as follows: first, a brief description of the climate database and the main global distribution of the tuning parameters is presented; second, the numerical model used to compute the performance of the converter is introduced, and the characteristics of the WEC are presented; finally, the results of the different options are analyzed in terms of the CWR and the KWT for each of the proposed options.

2. Climate data

A global climate database is required to analyze WEC global power production. In this study, a global wave reanalysis database is used (GOW1.0) (7) (8). GOW 1.0 is based on a NCEP/NCAR atmospheric forcing reanalysis (9), which constitutes one of the longest and most up-to-date global re-analyses. This database provides spectral sea-state parameters (significant wave height (H_s), mean period (T_m), peak period (T_p) and mean direction (θ_m)) and directional spectra components, $S(f, \theta)$, along the coast. GOW 1.0 covers the period 1948-2008 at a $1^\circ \times 1.5^\circ$ global resolution. For the present analysis, 1188 GOW 1.1 nodes along the world shorelines have been selected with an average spacing of 200 km. This database has been calibrated with satellite data and globally validated with buoy data.

In this study, the following three sea state parameters are used:

- Wave height (H_s). H_s is notable because the wave energy is related to the square of the wave height. H_s is also important in terms of WEC survivability because WECs must be designed to survive extreme conditions.
- Wave incident direction (θ). The performance of several WECs depends on the wave direction, and the performance of wave energy farms also depends on the spatial distribution of WECs relative to wave direction.
- Peak period (T_p). The performance of the floating WECs depends on the matching the wave period of the incoming waves with the natural period of the floating device.

Although all of these variables are important and necessary in the study of wave energy converters, the direction and wave height are not key variables regarding the tunability of a wave energy converter. The peak period will be the key parameter investigated in this study.

The GOW database offers global information. WEC farms will be first deployed on continental shelves away from the breaking zone. For this study, 1188 GOW 1.0 nodes located between 50 and 100 m of

water depth around global coastlines have been selected. In this analysis, the prospective wave energy farm is assumed to be deployed in deep water (>50 m), consequently the GOW database can be used without further propagation modeling.

Figure 1 shows several statistical parameters used to characterize the T_p of the selected nodes. The upper left panel shows the average peak period, μ_{T_p} . Globally, the variability of μ_{T_p} is high. The lowest values of μ_{T_p} (less than 5 s) are found in enclosed seas (i.e., the Mediterranean) that are dominated by low fetch SEA waves; whereas the highest values (higher than 12 s) are found along coasts that are dominated mainly by SWELL waves (Indian Sea Indonesia; Pacific Central America) or by highly developed SEAS (Southwest Australia). Intermediate to low values (between 6 and 9 s) are found in the east-oriented oceanic coasts that are attacked primarily by long fetch SEA waves (Atlantic North and South America; Pacific Japan, New Guinea and Australia). Finally, medium to high periods (between 9 and 12 s) are encountered on west-oriented oceanic coasts attacked by SEA and SWELL waves (Atlantic Europe and Africa; Pacific North America and Southern Chile).

Figure 1: Average T_p (s), standard deviation of T_p (s), coefficient of variation of T_p and mode of T_p (s)

The upper right and the lower left panels of figure 1 show the standard deviation, σ_{T_p} , and the coefficient of variation, $C_{vT_p} = \sigma_{T_p}/\mu_{T_p}$, of the peak periods, respectively. Both parameters are relevant in the understanding of the variability in the peak period parameter and the shape of the distribution. The lowest values, $C_{vT_p} \leq 0.2$, correspond to those south- and west-oriented coastlines that are governed by constant SEAs or SWELLS and are exposed to the southern Pacific waves generated by the roaring forties or in those eastern-oriented Atlantic, Indian and Pacific coasts submitted to the developed SEAs generated by the trade winds. Intermediate C_{vT_p} values between 0.2 and 0.4 correspond to the majority of the remaining coastline. These values indicate that the variability of the peak period is higher in these areas, and although tuning of a WEC is possible, the influence of the wave period on WEC design is higher and should be considered. The highest values, $C_{vT_p} > 0.4$, are found in enclosed seas (i.e., the Timor Sea coast in northwest Australia), along which the SEAs display a higher rate of variability.

Finally, the bottom right panel of figure 1 shows the modal value of the peak period. Comparing this panel with the μ_{T_p} , the modal value of T_p is higher than the mean globally, indicating a negative skewness of the T_p distribution (a longer upper tail than the lower tail).

Spectral parameters in the database can be used to compute the global energy resource in deep waters (assuming seas have a Pierson-Moskowitz spectrum with $T_p \approx 1.4T_{(1,0)}$) by using the International Energy Agency's formula for the sea state mean energy flux:

$$F_e (W/m) \cong 577 H_s^2 T_z \cong 412 H_s^2 T_p$$

Figure 2 shows the average, μ_{F_e} , the standard deviation, σ_{F_e} , and the coefficient of variation, C_{vF_e} , of the wave energy flux, F_e (kW/m). The variability in the wave energy resource is high around the globe. The areas with the highest energy resource (60-80 kW/m) correspond to the high latitudes (Northwest Europe, Northwest America and the Southwest portion of America, Africa and Australia). The tropical and

subtropical areas have lower power resources and the lowest variations. The coefficients of variation in the high latitudes of the Northern hemisphere and in the enclosed seas show the highest variability.

Figure 2: Average (kW/m), standard deviation (kW/m) and coefficient of variation of wave energy resources

3.-Frequency domain analysis

The numerical model used in this study is a previously described frequency domain model (10). This type of model is useful for the early stages of development of a converter because of the low computational requirements. By considering that nonlinearities are small, the superposition principle can be used. Then, a linear model is constructed.

This type of model has been widely explained and previously used (11) (12). The equations of motion for a rigid body system (with 6 degrees of freedom, DOF) in sea waves can be described with the following equation:

$$-\omega^2 m |\hat{z}| e^{i\omega t} = A(\omega) \hat{f}_{exc}(\omega) e^{i\omega t} - G |\hat{z}| e^{i\omega t} + \omega^2 M(\omega) |\hat{z}| e^{i\omega t} - i\omega B(\omega) |\hat{z}| e^{i\omega t} - i\omega D(\omega) |\hat{z}| e^{i\omega t} - K(\omega) |\hat{z}| e^{i\omega t}$$

[1]
where

- z is complex amplitude of motion of each degree of freedom
- ω is the radial frequency in rad/s;
- m is the mass of the floating object;
- $A(\omega)$ is the amplitude of the incident wave;
- $\hat{f}_{exc}(\omega)$ is the complex amplitude of the excitation force of a wave with a frequency ω and unit wave;
- G is the hydrostatic coefficient;
- $M(\omega)$ is the added mass considered as a function of ω ;
- $B(\omega)$ is the hydrodynamic damping coefficient considered as a function of ω ; and

- $K(\omega)$ and $D(\omega)$ are the PTO coefficients that depend on ω .

This equation is time dependent because of the term $e^{i\omega t}$. However, this term can be neglected because it is present in all other terms of the equation. Then, equation 1 can be rewritten as a time independent equation:

$$-\omega^2 \mathbf{m} |\hat{Z}| = \mathbf{A}(\omega) \hat{f}_{exc} - \mathbf{G} |\hat{Z}| + \omega^2 \mathbf{M}(\omega) |\hat{Z}| - i\omega \mathbf{B}(\omega) |\hat{Z}| - i\omega \mathbf{D}(\omega) |\hat{Z}| - \mathbf{K}(\omega) |\hat{Z}| \quad [2]$$

If the previous equation is expressed for one floater with 6 DOFs, this equation can be written in the following matrix form (it is assumed that the PTO only):

$$[-\omega^2 (m + M) + G + i[\omega(B + D)]] \times [Z] = [F_{ex}] \quad [3]$$

where

- m is the inertia matrix of the floating object;
- M is the added mass matrix of the floating object that accounts for the added mass of each DOF k when a displacement is produced in a DOF j . If several bodies are considered, then the added mass matrix contains the added mass that it is produced on a body a on a DOF k when a displacement is produced on body b in a DOF j ;
- G is the matrix of hydrostatic coefficients;
- B is the damping matrix of the floating object that contains the added mass of each DOF k when a displacement is produced in a DOF j . If several bodies are considered, then the added mass matrix contains the added mass that is produced on a body a on a DOF k when a displacement is produced on body b in a DOF j ;
- D_{PTO} is the power take-off matrix in which the coefficients appear as the degree of freedom that reflects how the converter extracts energy; and
- Z is the complex amplitude of motion of each degree of freedom. In this equation, the incident wave height is assumed to be 1 m. Afterwards, the real incident wave will be considered.

Once the system of equations is solved, the amplitude of motion for each degree of freedom variable is computed. Then, the absorbed power can be calculated. The time series of displacements that accounts for the amplitude of motion by computing the frequency domain model is as follows:

$$\eta(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N A_i(\omega_i) a_{Di}(\omega_i) \sin(\omega_i t + \varphi_i) \quad [4]$$

where $A_i(\omega_i)$ is the amplitude of the incident wave, $a_{Di}(\omega_i)$ is the motion response obtained by the frequency domain model for the DOF that extracts the energy for a certain frequency and φ_i is the phase of the motion.

The power time series can be obtained as the following equation:

$$P(t) = D [\sum_{i=1}^N \omega_i A_i(\omega_i) a_{Di}(\omega_i) \cos(\omega_i t + \varphi_i)]^2 \quad [5]$$

where D the optimum PTO constant for the frequency ω_i . For a sea state of N spectral components, the mean power of a sea state can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P} &= \frac{1}{S} \int_0^S P(t) dt = \frac{D}{S} \int_0^S \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \omega_i A_i(\omega_i) a_{Di}(\omega_i) \cos(\omega_i t + \varphi_i) \right]^2 dt \\ \bar{P} &= \frac{D}{S} \int_0^S \sum_{i=1}^N [\omega_i A_i(\omega_i) a_{Di}(\omega_i) \cos(\omega_i t + \varphi_i)]^2 dt \\ &\quad + \frac{D}{S} \int_0^S \sum_{i \neq j}^N 2\omega_i \omega_j A_i A_j a_{Di} a_{Dj} \cos(\omega_i t + \varphi_i) \cos(\omega_j t + \varphi_j) dt \end{aligned}$$

[6]

The average of the second integral can be assumed to be zero if S (duration of the sea state) is large; therefore, the solution of the first square cosine integral is $S/2$. Then, the mean power absorbed by a floating converter within a sea state can be computed with the following expression:

$$\bar{P} = \frac{D}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N [\omega_i A_i(\omega_i) a_{Di}(\omega_i)]^2 \quad [7]$$

Applying this procedure, the power matrix of a device can be obtained. For each sea state, a unique PTO constant is applied. The PTO constant is the value that maximizes the mean absorbed power for a regular wave train with a period equal to the peak period (T_p) of the sea state. Consequently, only one PTO constant exists per sea state.

4.-WEC Characteristics

The selected WEC resembles the Wavestar prototype (13), consisting of a central body that is fixed or floating and a series of floaters on both sides of the central body (figure 3). These floats are connected to the main body with arms and are allowed to move only in heaving motions. A hydraulic piston acts on the arms to transfer the motion of the floaters into mechanical energy. The main difference with the Wavestar prototype is that the motion is not circular and the floaters are assumed to only move in heave. To simplify the analysis and the tuning process of the floats, a set of cylinders is selected for this study. This simple design was selected to easily tune the floaters because the objective of this paper does not include studying the feasibility or behavior of this design.

Three geometric options are analyzed. First, floaters with a heave natural frequency of 4 s are suitable for enclosed seas and will behave as wave followers for larger wave periods. Second, floaters are tuned to resonate at 8 s (similar to the mean North Atlantic wave period). Third, a tunable converter is designed for periods of 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 s. Each of the sub-options are applied for the most probable period of each location to match the converter with the local met-ocean conditions for each site (see Table 1).

Figure 3: Set of floaters analysed as a converter

For this stage of research, a cylinder is then selected with a height equal to its diameter. The dimensions of the cylinders change for each option. Different draft/diameter ratios may lead to "lighter" structures; in this study, however, this ratio has been kept constant for the sake of simplicity and to limit the number of options. As expected, the natural period increases with the dimensions of the cylinder. Consequently, larger structures with a high draft are used when a high natural period is required. Table 1 presents a summary of the main parameters considered in this analysis.

In this case, the wave direction has not been considered, and the waves are assumed to propagate aligned with the direction of the floats (head seas). Floats are separated by $1.5 D$ (D : Diameter), and the two rows of floats are separated by $5 D$. A BEM software by HydroD (DNV) frequency domain numerical model is used for this analysis. This DNV program provides the coefficients required to perform the frequency domain analysis and to construct the power matrices. The central body is assumed to be fixed and emerged.

Characteristics/Option	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3 (Tunable converter)				
Natural period	4 s	8 s	4 s	6s	8s	10 s	12 s
Diameter of the float	4 m	15 m	4 m	8 m	15 m	20 m	28 m
Draft	3,5 m	14 m	3,5 m	8 m	14 m	19 m	27 m
Mass	38 Ton	2170 Ton	38 Ton	308 Ton	2170 Ton	6100 Ton	16.308 Ton

Table 1: Characteristics of the proposed options

Figure 4 shows the response amplitude operator (RAO) for all considered floats. Although these figures show the heave behavior of the individual floats, the computation of the power matrices considers the interaction between floats.

Using the previously described frequency domain model, the power matrix of each option is calculated. First, the optimum PTO damping constant for each period is obtained by running the numerical model with a set of PTO constants. Figure 5 shows the WEC power absorption in terms of the damping constant of an 8-s converter for regular waves with period 10.5 s. A maximum power production is achieved for a PTO constant of $1.2E6$ Nm/s. The observed motion amplitude at the optimum damping value is 0.9 m. This procedure is replicated for every period to obtain each individual optimum PTO constant (figure 7). Because a linear theory is applied, the optimum PTO constant does not depend on the incident wave amplitude. When calculating the power matrix, an identical PTO constant is applied for all floats.

Figure 4: Response amplitude operator of the individual floats for the proposed converters

Figure 5: Power and amplitude of motion as a function of the PTO constant for the 8-s converter (individual float)

Figure 6: Average Power and selected PTO Constant for each period for the 8 s converter (individual float)

After calculating the optimum damping constant, the power matrices of all geometries are computed. These values are calculated by applying the optimum damping that corresponds to a period equal to the peak period assigned to the bin of the Hs-Tp matrix. Figure 7 shows the power matrices that are obtained without any restriction in terms of nominal power or maximum vertical motion. Although figures 5 and 6 are shown for a single cylinder, the power matrices displayed in figure 7 are obtained by considering the interaction between cylinders.

Each matrix shows a peak in power production in the corresponding natural period. For each power matrix, the power production reaches a minimum for periods lower than the natural period. This result also coincides with the trends displayed in figures 4 and 6. However, as the dimensions of the cylinders increase, the power production increases. In the next section, the results are computed in terms of capture width ratio to avoid the influence of the diameter of the cylinder on power performance.

Figure 7: Power matrix (kW) of the designed converters (4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 s)

5.-Results

Local wave climate characteristics have not been previously considered in this analysis. With the power matrices for all geometries computed, the mean annual power absorbed by each WEC option at each location has been calculated by multiplying the Hs-Tp mean regime (scatter plot in %) at each node (obtained from the GOW1.0 database) by the power matrix.

$$\text{Annual Mean Power Production (kW)} = \text{Scatterplot (\%)} \times \text{Power Matrix (kW)}$$

To compare the effects of tuning on the efficiency of the devices, the results are shown in terms of capture width ratio (CWR) for a virtual cylinder with the WEC diameter. This parameter is calculated with the following formula; see (1) :

$$CWR = \frac{\text{Annual mean Power Production(kW)}}{\text{Wave energy Resource(kW)} \times \text{Number of floats} \times \text{Width of the floats}}$$

Figure 8 shows option 3 (tunable option; 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 s design) in which the WEC geometry used for each node is shown (considering the most probable period of the local met-ocean conditions). Almost 35% of the nodes match with the 8 s option (this value is the most probable global wave period), approximately 28 % for the 6-s option, 23% for the 10 s option, 15% for the 12 s option and 5 % for the 4 s option. Geometries with natural periods of 6 s, 8 s and 10 s are predominant. Figure 9 shows the CWR for the 3 options considered. As observed in the upper panel, the 4 s geometry has the only acceptable CWR values that range between 15 and 18% in several of the enclosed seas dominated by short SEA

Figure 8: Distribution of the converter used on each location for the option C (Tuned converter) in seconds

waves. In other oceanic areas, the 4 s geometry behaves as wave followers, and the capture ratio decreases; the CWR is still 10% in oceanic coastal areas oriented to the East with predominant SEA waves.

The middle panel of figure 9 shows the CWR for the 8 s geometry. In this case, the natural period for the converter better matches the mix of the ocean SEA and SWELLS encountered in the western ocean margins and the SWELLS of tropical coasts with CWRs between 15 and 20%. The maximum CWR values (>20%) correspond to tropical coasts oriented to the south in the Arabian Sea and on the Pacific coast of the Philippine Islands. As shown in Figure 1, these areas are characterized by a most probable period of 8 s; therefore, the CWR is at a maximum. As this WEC geometry performance decays rapidly for wave periods below 8 s, the enclosed seas have low CWR values (<5%).

The bottom panel of figure 9 shows the CWRs obtained with the tunable device. In this case, the CWR is medium to high in almost all areas. The maximum values of close to 25% are encountered in coastal areas under a constant SWELL or fully developed SEAs, such as the coasts north and west of the Iberian Peninsula, the west coast of Chile, the south and west coasts of Australia or the southwest coast of Indonesia. Coastal areas experience more variable climates because the enclosed seas or the Eastern continental margins have lower CWR values (between 15 and 20%). Normally, capturing wave energy contained in waves is easier for high periods (SWELLS), and the CWR is maximum in areas with periods higher than 8 s because the efficiency of the harvest is higher.

Tuning a WEC for each location (and each climate characteristics) therefore improves the CWR. For example, in the Mediterranean Sea, the 4 s geometry has a 12% average CWR; the 8 s geometry has a 5% average CWR and a 17% average CWR if the WEC is tuned for that climate. In the case of Southern Chile, the average CWR for the 4 s geometry is 7%; the 8-s geometry has a 20% average CWR and a

Figure 9: Capture width ratio (%) for option 1, 2 and 3

25% average CWR if the WEC is tuned for that climate. Table 2 shows the mean, standard deviation and several useful percentages of the CWR parameter computed for the entire set of nodes. Globally, option 1 has the lowest average CWR (10%). Option 2, tuned for a period near 8 s, has an average CWR of 15%. The tuned option has a 19% CWR. The percentages of nodes within certain CWR ranges are also shown. For a CWR higher than 15%, option 3 displays a 72% value, indicating a high conversion efficiency at many points. However, the percentages of nodes with a CWR higher than 15% corresponds to 67% for option 2. Consequently the tuned option improved the CWR by 4% and 9% with respect to option 2 and 1, respectively. However, if the results were analyzed from a local perspective, the tuned option would display higher differences with respect to the other two options. Therefore, redesigning a WEC for the climate of the deployment site improves efficiency.

Parameters	Average CWR (%)	Standard deviation CWR (%)	% of nodes with CWR<5	% of nodes with 5<CWR<15	% of nodes with CWR>15
Option 1	10	3	0.001	94	5.99
Option 2	15	5	3	30	67
Option 3	19	3	0.01	27	72.99

Table 2: Analysis of CWR values for the different options

Although the CWR parameter is an indicator of the WEC energy capture efficiency, this value does not provide any information about the economic performance of the device.

From an economic perspective, the cost of the WEC structure is one of the key factors in the WEC budget. According to previous studies (14), the marine structure accounts for nearly 40% of the budget of a WEC. To establish an indicator of the economic performance of the three proposed options, the indicator of kW/Ton (KWT onwards) will be used. This parameter relates the power produced to the WEC mass and has been previously used as an indicator of the economic performance (6). Numerically higher factors indicate a better economic performance.

Figure 10 shows the KWT maps for the three proposed options. The upper panel of figure 10 displays the case of the 4-s geometry; the highest value of this indicator appears in South Chile, with a KWT of approximately 0.7 kW/T. High KWT values (between 0.4 and 0.6) are also found in South and Southwest Australia, West Ireland, West Scotland, the northwest of France and Spain, South Iceland, West Canada and the Pacific Shores of the Aleutian Islands. However, the device is not tuned for these wave climates; the lightness of the structure and the capability of the WEC wave follower allow this option to be competitive in these high-energy/high-period areas. The areas in which the WEC is tuned to the wave climate (i.e., the Mediterranean or North Sea) have low KWT values (0.05 kW/Ton) because of low energy production.

The middle panel shows the KWT map for the 8 s WEC geometry. In this case, the KWT values are approximately one order of magnitude lower than the 4 s geometry case. Discarding the general KWT drop, the map is similar to the 4-s geometry map.

The bottom panel shows the KWT map for the tuned converter. In this case, the values are low. Most of

Figure 10: KWT for the three studied options

the enclosed seas that are tuned to 4-6 s (low WEC mass, see figure 11) have low energy fluxes (i.e., low production, see figure 12), and coasts with high energy fluxes are tuned to high periods, indicating high structural costs. Only small areas, such as the coasts of Holland, Germany and Denmark along the North Sea, have slightly better values. The North Sea is well suited for the 4 s device, and the energy flow is not as low as other enclosed seas. To support this analysis, figure 11 shows that the increase of WEC mass depends on the WEC natural period (a cubic fit is included in figure 11). From this analysis, smaller structures are advantageous when considering the power production versus mass.

To compare the KWT of the WEC options, figure 13 shows the relative KWT between pairs of options. If KWT_1 and KWT_2 are the indexes for a given point corresponding to WEC options 1 and 2, then the relative KWT is defined by the expression:

$$100 (KWT_1 - KWT_2)/KWT_2$$

The top panel of figure 13 shows the relative KWT between Option 2 ($T_n=8$ s) and Option 3 (Tuned converter). The values are positive in almost all locations, indicating that option 2 has higher KWT values in almost all locations. Along the Atlantic Coasts of Europe, the KWT values are 100% to 300% higher in option 2 than in option 3. These increased values are generated because the mass of the higher period options are greater than the low period options. Additionally, the power production does not increase at

an identical rate to the mass increases. In this comparison, the only areas that have negative values are the enclosed seas (i.e., the Mediterranean and North Sea) that are tuned with the low peak period options (4 and 6 s). Therefore, the tuned option has a lower mass and higher production than option 2.

Figure 11. WEC mass versus the natural period

Figure 12. Global WEC power production related to natural frequency

Figure 13. Relative KWT among WEC options pairs

The middle panel of figure 13 shows the relative KWT between options 3 (tuned converter) and option 1 ($T_n=4$ s). In this case, all values are negative, indicating that option 1 has higher KWT values than option 3 at all locations. Although option 1 is not tuned with all climates (just for the enclosed seas), the power production is high compared with the mass of the device. The tuned WECs in areas characterized with high peak periods (i.e., Western America or Atlantic Europe) require heavy structures.

The bottom panel of figure 13 shows the relative KWT between options 1 and 2. As in the previous case, all values are negative, indicating that option 1 is better than option 2 in terms of KWT at all locations (80 to 110 %). As the mass of option 2 (2170 ton) is 57 times the mass of option 1 (38 ton), the higher production obtained in those areas with a mean peak period near the resonant period of option 2 does not offset the cost of the difference in mass. Figure 12 shows the average KWT, the 5% quantile and the 95% quantile of the global KWT values in terms of the WEC peak period. Table 3 shows the KWT mean, standard deviation and the mean relative KWT between options.

Parameters	Average KWT	Standard deviation KWT	Mean KWT	
			Option 1	Option 3
Option 1	0.16	0.13	-----	
Option 2	0.02	0.019	-89%	88%
Option 3	0.025	0.02	-70%	

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation for the kW/Ton

The revenue from the increase in power production obtained by tuning the WEC to the mean peak period does not offset the cost increase of the structure of the WEC. The increase in power production of a tuned over a non-tuned converter (wave follower) is approximately 20% to 40%. However, a higher increase in the mass of the structure is required for high peak periods. Therefore, tuning the WEC to the mean peak

period is not necessary (except if the mean peak period is low), and the design of the converter should be directed to small marine structures that are wave followers.

The KWT parameter described above could be used as an indicator of the economic viability of the WEC in the studied location. To transform this indicator into Euros/kWh (€kWh), the following assumptions are drawn:

- Only the mass of the WEC floats are considered. These floats are supposed to be constructed with reinforced concrete.
- The WEC operative life is 25 years
- The cost of reinforced concrete is 500 Euros/m³ (high performance concrete)

With these assumptions, the KWT is converted to a €kWh indicator. This indicator is not a valid parameter for economic analyses because numerous additional costs should be considered to assess the real WEC cost. However, the €kWh parameter could be used to compare different locations.

From the point of view of a developer, the goal of the design of a WEC is to obtain a converter that could be deployed with a good performance in as many locations as possible. Therefore, two scenarios are imposed to determine appropriate locations for wave energy farms. The following two conditions are imposed (see Table 4):

- In terms of CWR, a minimum value is selected. A previous study (15) investigated the CWR for a set of converters using numerical modeling and experimental testing. For the case of small heaving buoys, a range in CWRs (from 9% to 14 %) was achieved. For the large buoys, a CWR range of 19 to 41% was attained. In this analysis, a 10% CWR minimum is used for the two proposed scenarios.
- In terms of KWT, different minimum values are used for each of the two scenarios to study which locations comply with the restriction: 0.01 KWT (0.1 €kWh) and 0.1 KWT (0.01 €kWh). The second restriction could be near the current energy cost scenario in numerous locations.

Characteristics/Option	Condition 1	Condition 2
CWR	>10%	>10%
KWT / €kWh	>0.1 / >0.01	>0.01 / > 0.1

Table 4: Proposed scenarios for the study

Locations that satisfy these conditions are suitable for wave energy farms (YES), otherwise areas labeled with a NO. Finally a sensitivity analysis in terms of the percentage of available locations restricted by the CWR and KWT is performed. This analysis is shown in Figure 15 and Figure 16.

Panels on the left-hand side of Figure 14 show the available coastal locations for Scenario 1 and the different WEC options. For option 1 (4 s natural period; upper panel), approximately all locations satisfy the conditions. If option 2 is selected (8 s natural period, middle left panel), those regions with peak periods far from 8 s (i.e., the Mediterranean) with low peak periods and low energy waves or the West coast of Central America with high peak periods and low energy waves do not satisfy condition 1. Finally, for option 3 (tuned converter; bottom left panel), the locations that do not satisfy condition 1 are those areas with high peak periods and low wave energy (i.e., tropical Pacific America, Tropical Atlantic Africa or the southern coast of Arabia, India or Indonesia).

Panels on the right-hand side of figure 14 show the available coastal locations identified by the more restrictive, in terms of KWT, condition 2 and the different WEC options. For option 1 (upper right panel), those areas with low wave energy (enclosed seas as the Mediterranean and several tropical areas) do not satisfy the conditions. the Mediterranean Sea and other enclosed seas do not satisfy condition 2 despite the good CWR in the oceanic areas because of the high peak periods. If option 2 is selected (middle right panel), only those areas with high mean wave energy fluxes and medium to high peak periods (Northwest Europe, South Iceland and Greenland in the Atlantic; Alaska, part or Aleutian Islands and Southwest Chile in the Pacific; South Africa, Southwest Australia and New Zealand) comply with condition 2.

Figure 14. Available coastal locations for Scenarios 1 and 2 and the different WEC options

For option 2, only few locations satisfy the conditions. The remaining locations that satisfy both conditions are located in Northern Europe (Scotland) and South America (Chile). These places have high wave energy resources. Finally, if an option 3 device is selected (tunable; bottom right panel), several coastal areas display medium energy with low peak periods of approximately 6 s (the North African Mediterranean Coast of Tunisia and Libya, southern coasts of the North Sea, the south coast of Newfoundland and other small areas). Regions with high wave energy fluxes and high periods that were acceptable for Scenario 2 for WECs tuned for 8 s (option 2) are unacceptable when tuned for the location peak period. Tuning for the location is unacceptable because of the high cost of the structure. However, for option 3 on the Mediterranean, several differences are shown for scenario 2. This is because the most probable period of these locations ranges from 4 to 7 s, and then when option 3 is applied, different sub-options are applied for different points.

Option 1 (4 s converter) has the most possibilities in terms of availability of locations, and tuning a converter for each met-ocean condition does not provide a positive effect on the cost of the extracted energy. In other words, smaller floaters produce higher KWTs. This statement should be taken with care because other costs (PTO costs, O&M costs, etc.) that may decrease as the floater size increases have not been considered in this analysis.

Finally, to separate the influence of the two studied variables (CWR and KWT), a sensitivity analysis is performed. This analysis is conducted in terms of the percentage of locations at which the CWR or the KWT is lower than a certain value.

Figure 15 shows the percentage of available locations with a CWR higher than a selected value for the three WEC geometries. As observed in figure 15, the tuned converter always displays higher CWRs than the other two options. Option 2 is slightly below the tuned converter for medium to high CWRs but is well below the tunable option for medium to low CWR. This behavior is because the 8-s tuning restricts those locations with low mean peak periods. Finally, the option 1 curve (4-s WEC natural period) falls below the other two because the 4 s converter is only tuned for a few locations. For instance, in the case of an option 1 WEC, 5% of locations have CWRs higher than 15% whereas the percentage of locations are 12% and 75% for option 2 and 3, respectively.

Figure 16 shows the percentage of available locations with KWT values higher than a selected value for the three WEC geometries. As observed in figure 16, the differences between option 1 (WEC with 4 s natural period) and the other two options are notable. Option 1 is applicable to many more locations than the other two options. The difference between the curves for options 2 and 3 and the curve for option 1 is due to the low mass required by option 1 compared with the other two. Option 2 (8 s converter) and 3 (tunable option) display similar curves. Both of these curves converge to an identical KWT of 0.12 (0.09 Euros/kWh). Option 2 and option 3 converge when the percentages of locations lowers. This is because the value was inferred for section 1 and the most probable period around the world coastlines is 8 s. Therefore, the convergence is unsurprising.

Figure 15: Percentage of available locations depending on CWR

Figure 16: Percentage of available locations depending on the KWT indicator

6.-Conclusions

In this study, an analysis of the adaptability of a generic Wave Energy Converter (WEC) to different climate conditions was conducted. The studied converter mimics the Wave Star device and consists of two rows of cylinders aligned in the wave propagation direction to absorb energy during heaving motion. Three options are proposed: a converter tuned to a period typical of the enclosed seas (option 1; 4 s converter), a converter tuned to the typical Atlantic swell (option 2; 8 s converter) and a tunable option (option 3; variable converter 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 seconds). The power matrices are calculated with a frequency domain model.

The adaptability of these options to the global, coastal wave climate is studied using the met-ocean data extracted from the global reanalysis database GOW 1.0 (7). For this analysis, two indicators (Capture Width Ratio (CWR) and kW/Ton (KWT)) are assessed to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of resonant tuning the WEC.

The CWR indicator represents the efficiency of the converter with respect to the available resource at the location. Because option 1 is tuned to low-peak period locations that are typical of enclosed seas, the CWR for this option in ocean locations with medium- to high-peak periods is low. However, option 2 (8 s converter) has good CWR values on these oceanic coasts with medium to high peak periods, whereas these converters perform poorly in low-peak period environments in the enclosed seas. Logically, the tunable WEC, option 3, adapts the best to all wave scenarios in terms of CWR.

The KWT indicator represents a type of “economic viability” indicator. The structure cost is related to the mass. The mass increases by a cube of the WEC natural period (see figure 11). Therefore, tuning the WEC to high periods implies heavy and costly structures. Globally, the higher KWT values are found for WEC option 1 although the converter is not tuned with the majority of the climates (in most cases, the floater follows the free surface). For example, the structure of an option 2 device is 80 times heavier than an option 1 structure, and the power production is only 30% higher at locations in which option 2 is tuned to its natural 8-s period. For option 3 (WEC tuned to the peak period), the KWT indicator is low in almost all locations, notably in locations characterized by high peak periods in which the tuning requires large structures without a comparable increase in power production (see (10)).

Therefore, tuning a converter for each location is positive in terms of efficiency but not advantageous in economic terms (KWT indicator). Considering that the cost of other factors that influence the overall cost of WECs (the number of PTOs for a given power, O&M) increase for smaller WECs, the main goal of a

WEC design should be to select for structures with a moderate size that are not tuned with the wave climate.

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